

D1.2 User guidelines

General information

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Executive Summary

The present deliverable D1.2 User guidelines – establishes the framework under which AgroServ consortium will implement TAVA projects.

AgroServ needs to provide guidelines for both Access Providers operating different facilities and services as well as for the users on how to utilize these services in an effective and transparent way. Particularly, the eligibility criteria are outlined, defining the very basic criteria to ensure TAVA provision according to HE regulations. Additionally, the document provides links to other relevant guidelines with detailed descriptions on how to address ethical issues, data management etc.

Finally, the document includes the description of the AgroServ TAVA procedures to demonstrate how these different guidelines are implemented in a way that ensures smooth and transparent access to facilities and services and, as such, enables to address key questions related to resilient and sustainable agriculture and transition towards agroecology

Glossary

Term	Description
Access	Access to the research infrastructures under the project AgroServ is provided free of charge to the User/User Groups once their proposals for the use of services have been approved and passed the eligibility criteria, and the feasibility and scientific evaluations during the selection phases. For more details see D1.3 AgroServ Access Policy
Access Manager	Manager of access and service provision in a Research Infrastructure (list of Access Managers Appendix 1)
Access Provider	Manage of a specific facility or service within an organisation that is a member of a Research infrastructure
User or User Group	The external committer of resources that exploits the transnational or virtual access services offered by the AgroServ project; the user can be an individual or a team of researchers from the public or private sector.
AgroServ	The present project providing integrated services to support the sustainable agroecological transition
DMP	Data Management Plan : guidelines for management of data within AgroServ
Facility or Installation	Facility or installation (used as synonyms) required for the implementation of a specific service, usually users obtain access to experimental providing specific services (experimentation, data analysis etc.)
Proposal Review Committee	Panel of independent experts that will assess the Transnational Access applications

RI	Facilities or installation that provide resources and services for the research communities to conduct research and foster innovation in their fields. For more details see D1.3 AgroServ Access Policy.
TAVA	Trans-National and Virtual Access allowing third party researchers from a foreign institution to access an organisation's research facilities (installations) and services (TA) and access to an organisation's cloud, data centre, and/or its other IT facilities and services such as data analysis/analysis pipeline set-up or other more "operational" components.
WP	Work Package. A set of related activities within a project.

1 Introduction

The goal of AgroServ is to support research and innovation by providing customised and integrated research infrastructure (RI) services in Europe with the goal to advance sustainable and resilient agriculture and support agroecological transitions. One of the key instruments is the provision of physical, remote and virtual services that will enable cross disciplinary research needed for agroecological transition. The research in this area is by nature cross-disciplinary, and AgroServ translational and virtual access (TAVA) has to enable interaction of communities of researchers in widely separated areas. Thus, AgroServ integrates diverse scientific expertise from 11 ESFRI RIs (both projects and landmarks) contributing to different aspects of agroecology (Figure 1). AgroServ will allow users access to scientific data, highly specialized expertise, experimental sites, technology and laboratories integrating competences from chemists, biologists, agronomists, ecologists, bio-engineers, analysts, sociologists, economists etc. The present document summarizes the guidelines for users utilizing TAVA to the services provided within the AgroServ project.

Figure 1: The RIs at the core of AgroServ

1.1 Objective and scope

The cross-disciplinary nature of the project provides challenges and opportunities, with the project aiming (within the TA/VA approach) to inspire users to seize the potential of the existing diversity of the available services to specifically support cross-disciplinary TA/VA projects. Thus, it is important to develop very clear rules and procedures for user access along the guidelines provided by the European Commission (the European Charter of Access for Research Infrastructures¹), complemented by specific requirements from different RIs. The goal is to ensure high-quality output based on the TA/VA services embedded in a sound legal and organizational framework. Specifically, the deliverable will address the

- access procedures;
- general guidelines for access;
- specific requirements related to feasibility related to data management according to the DMP, ethical issues, IPR etc.

2 User guidelines

User or User Groups that aim at using the TA/VA services are expected to specifically use the cross-disciplinary nature of AgroServ and user services from multiple RIs (at least two RIs) which are listed within AgroServ catalogue of services (Deliverable 2.1 Catalogue of Services). All the available services are described within the catalogue of services and all applications have to be submitted in an online application platform (Deliverable 1.1 Access portal). This is specifically included in the application procedure and supported by the guidelines to comply with formal rules at the EU and national level (Deliverable 1.3 AgroServ Access policy) and to ensure that the TA/VA projects are of high scientific quality.

2.1 Eligibility criteria for Transnational and Virtual Access

The general access criteria are outlined in the access guidelines provided by the EC, which are complemented by specific aspects of the AgroServ project. These criteria are published on the website and are also part of the application procedure.

- **TA/VA definition:**
 - Transnational and Virtual Access to AgroServ services is free of charge for its users and includes the logistical, technological and scientific support needed to use the services provided by the research facilities (=installation).
 - Transnational and Virtual Access in AgroServ aims at answering basic and applied questions related to sustainable and resilient agriculture and agroecological transition; it may address, for example, technological challenges, advancing agricultural practices or value chains, or related activities.
 - The Transnational and Virtual Access projects address cross-disciplinary topics related to agroecology and users should use at least two or more services of two or

¹ <https://op.europa.eu/en/publication-detail/-/publication/78e87306-48bc-11e6-9c64-01aa75ed71a1/>

more Research Infrastructures listed in the catalogue of services (Deliverable 2.1 Catalogue of Services).

- The Transitional Access can include the following types of services as often as a combination of services:
 - Physical Access: access in person, with users physically visiting the facility/installation and receiving the service “hands-on”; e.g., access to experimental facilities.
 - Remote access: the resources and services are offered to the users without the users physically visiting the facility: e.g., access to samples, bio stimulants etc.
 - Virtual Access: access to data or models including the organisation’s cloud, data centre, and/or its other IT facilities and services such as data analysis/analysis pipeline set-up or other more “operational” components.

- **Eligibility of applicants:**

- EU & Third Countries:
Access is free of charge for User Groups from EU Member States and EU Associated States and, within a limit of 20% of the total available capacity, to users outside of Europe in particularly from developing countries.
- Transnationality:
The majority of the user consortium (group leader and group members) must work in a country other than the country(ies) where the facilities/installations/services are located. Exceptions are International organizations, the Joint Research Centres (JRC), ERIC or similar legal entities.
- Dissemination of results:
Only User Groups that are allowed to disseminate the results they have generated under the TAVA access may benefit from the access, unless the users are working for SMEs.
- Further obligations:
Applicants commit to having obtained legal and ethical consent regarding their research, transfer of biological material, and their data management approaches prior to submitting their application. For details, see the related guidelines and policies (see chapter 2.2)

- **Further eligibility criteria:**

- Ethical aspects (Deliverable 4.2 Protocol for ethical assessment of the user's requests; Deliverable 9.3 General Ethical Guidelines)
- Data management policy (Deliverable 9.4 Project Data Management Plan)
- Access policy (Deliverable 1.3 Access policy)

- This is complemented by a set of templates with dedicated legal documents that support the TAVA implementation such as templates for TAVA agreement, Material Transfer Agreements etc.

2.2 Transnational and Virtual Access procedure

The TAVA procedure is an online procedure and described in detail in D1.2 (Access portal). The procedure consists of multiple steps (Fig. 2) that include a smooth submission and the optimization of the applications to ensure feasibility of the projects and their scientific quality. The services in AgroServ are very diverse, with nearly 150 specific services (see catalogue of services). While users can perform a search within the catalogue of services and select potential services, the practical implementation of these services requires a direct interaction between the users and RI experts to ensure sound and feasible TAVA projects. An important role in the procedure will be ensured by the panel of Access Managers, which consists of Access Manager representatives from each RI. The panel of Access Managers will support all the submitted pre-proposals (step 1 in Fig. 2) with the goal to optimize the pre-proposals by addressing the technical feasibility and cross-disciplinarity of the pre-proposals (intermediary step in Fig. 2). The Access Managers have an extensive overview of the facilities within their RI. Thus, they will ensure that the users will interact with facility managers, who operate the facilities on day to day basis to prepare feasible and sound full proposals that address the needs of the users (step 2 in Fig 2).

The full proposals will be submitted and evaluated by an independent reviewer panel (PRC) (Step 3, Fig. 2). This step includes scientific evaluation. While step 1 focuses on the eligibility and the feasibility of the TAVA projects, this step will address the scientific quality of the proposals.

After the selection of the proposal, the users can discuss with the facility provider the practical implementation of the proposed work (step 4 in Fig. 2) and will have to report about the obtained output (step 5 in Fig. 2).

Figure 2: The TAVA procedure

The procedure includes monitoring (mainly in the form of questionnaires towards users and Access Managers) of the TA/VA projects, that aims at continuous improvement of the procedure including improving the communication of the TA/VA calls (user questionnaire in step 1 Expression of Interest), optimizing the TA/VA procedure and support by Access Providers (user questionnaire in step 5 Reporting). All information obtained via the monitoring will be documented and treated in accordance with the GDPR requirements (Regulation (EU) 2016/679, see also D9.2 Data management plan).

Following a dedicated call for TA/VA proposals, the TA/VA procedure includes the following steps:

- **Step 1: Expression of interest by User Groups, description of intended work**
 - User Group selects services such as access to facilities, remote or virtual services listed in the catalogue of services (Deliverable 2.1 Catalogue of services). Please note: multiple services from at least two RIs should be selected to ensure cross-disciplinary projects.
 - Priority will be given to multi actor consortia such as for instance living labs which will be assessed by the Executive Board.
 - User Group submits a pre-proposal / expression of interest with a short description of the intended work including:
 - identification of the potential services (RIs)
 - description of the potential TA/VA proposal
 - expected outcome(s)
 - The panel of Access Managers, representing the access services representatives within the AgroServ Research Infrastructures, will support the User Groups of the pre-proposal / expression of interest by:
 - assessing the eligibility and feasibility
 - finding the required services (access/service providers)
 - facilitating cross-disciplinary
 - enabling feasible TA/VA projects
 - providing feedback to the applicants addressing the above-mentioned aspects

- **Step 2: full proposal**
 - User Group prepares a full proposal with the support of the access/service provider(s) to ensure the technical feasibility of the proposal
 - The proposal will include:
 - Description of the wider context and the contribution to agroecology
 - Detailed description of work plan
 - Scientific and technical feasibility addressed by key questions which will need to be answered by the applicant and the service provider(s) indicating agreement on (see also Deliverable 4.1 Harmonisation of access quality management and monitoring procedures for multi-RI TA/VA):
 - working regulations at the site(s), including insurance for the people involved
 - technical access to be provided (equipment, consumables)
 - technician support to be provided
 - measurement/analyses services to be provided

- conditions of access to data and background knowledge of the host organisation(s)
 - conditions for reimbursement by host organization have been explained to the user (forms, condition of reporting etc.)
 - use and insurance of instruments brought by the user during the project
 - sharing, reporting and publishing of the data and research results
 - the TA/VA application has been evaluated and both the applicant seeking access and the host facility(ies) have confirmed the project
 - the user and the host have agreed on the conditions of project authorization regarding ethics and animal experimentation.
- Output section with:
 - estimation of the expected impact
 - ethical self-assessment
 - data management aspects
 - intellectual property aspects
 - conflict of interest
 - The proposals will be formally checked for technical eligibility by the access management office.
 - Eligible proposals will be evaluated by a panel of Independent External Reviewers (see step 3).
 - Selected proposals should then negotiate directly with the facility manager the details of the TA/VA and are requested to provide a final report after finalizing the TA/VA project considering all relevant guidelines and policies (D1.2 AgroServ access policies, D4.1 Guidelines on the harmonisation of access quality management and monitoring procedures for multi-RI TA/VA).
- **Step 3: Evaluation**
 - Evaluation will be done by a Proposal Review Committee (PRC) composed of independent external reviewers.
 - Evaluation criteria:
 - innovative nature of the proposal, including cross-disciplinary approach
 - scientific quality
 - implementation
 - expected output and impact
 - The PRC may ask the applicants for further information or ask additional expert for their assessment in to evaluate the proposal.
 - Proposals will be evaluated and ranked according to their scientific merit and compliance with the agroecology framework of the research.
 - **Step 4 Implementation of access**
 - Consortia of selected proposals are free to negotiate between the users and Access Providers the details of the implementation of the TA/VA project to ensure the best possible implementation and outcome considering all relevant guidelines and policies (D1.2 AgroServ access policies, D4.1 Guidelines on the harmonisation of access quality management and monitoring procedures for multi-RI TA/VA).
 - Users are expected to be directly involved in carrying out the proposed work.
 - Travel costs are covered by the TA/VA programme for the physical access.

- We strongly recommend the use of “User access contract” in every TA/VA defining the roles of users and Access Providers, their duties and obligations.
 - Templates will be provided: TA/VA contract, MTA
- **Step 5 Reporting and feedback**
 - Users and Access Providers are responsible for the delivery of access reports during and after the finalization of the TA/VA projects. If the TA/VA project exceed 6 months a mid-term report is requested and the final report is requested 1 month after the end of the project.
 - Video reporting is optional
 - The report should include:
 - duration of the access and its type (physical, remote, virtual)
 - description of the performed work
 - summary of the main findings
 - expected publications (including presentations)
 - data management plan
 - User feedback to monitor the quality of user access: online survey (WP4)
 - Dissemination of project results:
 - The optimisation of the impact of publicly-funded scientific research is important and results are expected to be published according to Open Science criteria in open access journals (for details see Deliverable 1.3 AgroServ Access policies);
 - Users are supposed to acknowledge AgroServ and the facilities accessed when presenting the results obtained within the TA/VA scheme (e.g., in presentations, publications etc). The acknowledgement of AgroServ is obligatory, the proposed acknowledgement text: "The research leading to these results has received funding from the AgroServ project, under the European Union Horizon Europe research and innovation programme".

3 References

- Guidelines from RIs involved in AgroServ
- European charter of access for research infrastructures
(<https://op.europa.eu/en/publication-detail/-/publication/78e87306-48bc-11e6-9c64-01aa75ed71a1/>)
- Deliverable 1.1 Access portal
- Deliverable 1.3 AgroServ Access policy
- Deliverable 2.1 Catalogue of services
- Deliverable 4.1 Harmonisation of Access quality management and monitoring procedures for multiRI TA/VA
- Deliverable 9.1 Communication plan
- Deliverable 9.3 General Ethical guidelines
- Deliverable 9.4 Project Data Management Plan

Appendix 1

A1 Access Manager

In this appendix we provide Access Managers from each research infrastructure.

RI	Access Manager	Contact details
AnaEE	Lavanya Premvardhan Klaus Steenberg Larsen	lavanya.premvardhan@anaee.eu ksl@ign.ku.dk
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